

Modulation of Deformation by Magmatic Tempo, Coast Mountains Batholith, British Columbia, Canada

Margaret E. Rusmore¹, Glenn J. Woodsworth², M. Robinson Cecil³, Harold H. Stowell⁴, Elizabeth Bollen⁴, George E. Gehrels⁵, Marty Grove⁶, and Pinkie Young¹

¹Occidental College; ²Geological Survey of Canada; ³California State University, Northridge; ⁴University of Alabama; ⁵University of Arizona; ⁶Stanford University

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Figures S1, S2 and S3; Figure S2

Introduction

S1: This file contains weighted mean and concordia plots for all 14 samples dated as part of this study. Tables with individual zircon grain data are provided in a separate file (Supplemental data table S01_U-Pb_Rusmore et al) at Dryad. Zircon U-Pb are also available at the Geochron database repository (<http://geochron.org/>).

Figure S1-1. Concordia plot (a) and weighted mean plots (b and c) for sample 14MR13.

Figure S1-2. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR27. Blue bars in b are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-3. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR33.

Figure S1-4. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR34. Blue bars in b are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-5. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR40. Blue bars in b are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-6. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR46. Blue bars in b are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age. Ellipses in (a) and bars in (b) are color-coded by zircon U/Th. The three youngest grains excluded in (b) all have high (>200) U/Th.

Figure S1-7. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR50. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-8. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 14MR59. Gray ellipse in (a) and white bar in (b) is an analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age. Ellipses in (a) and bars in (b) are color-coded by zircon U/Th.

Figure S1-9. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 15MR01. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-10. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 15MR02. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-11. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 15MR03. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-12. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 15MR05. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

Figure S1-13. Concordia (a) and weighted mean (b) plot for sample 15MR21. Blue bars in (b) are analyses excluded in the calculation of the weighted mean age.

S2: Ar spectra for dated samples. See also: Supplemental data table S02_Ar data table_Rusmore et al., Dryad

S3: This file contains annotated BSE images of the five samples used for hornblende geothermobarometry, showing spots analyzed.

2727R08

MR111016_Image-1_2727R08-1219-1

MR111016_Image-2_2727R08-1219-2

MR111016_Image-3_2727R08-1217-1

MR111016_Image-4_2727R08-1217-3

MR111016_Image-5_2727R08-1223-1

MR111016_Image-6_2727R08-1221-3

14MR68

MR111016_Image-7_14MR68-1199-1

MR111016_Image-8_14MR68-1199-2

MR111016_Image-9_14MR68-1195-1

MR111016_Image-11_14MR68-1193-1

MR111016_Image-12_14MR68-1191-1

MR111016_Image-13_14MR68-1189-1

MR111016_Image-14_14MR68-1189-2

MR111016_Image-15_14MR72-1207-1

MR111016_Image-16_14MR68-1209-1-2

14MR72

MR111016_Image-17_14MR72-1209-1

MR111016_Image-18_14MR72-1209-1

MR111016_Image-19_14MR72-1205-1-2

MR111016_Image-20_14MR72-1205-3

MR111016_Image-21_14MR72-1203-1

MR111016_Image-22_14MR72-1213-1

MR111016_Image-26_14MR72-1167-2a

MR111016_Image-27_14MR72-1167-3

MR111016_Image-28_14MR72-1171-1

MR111016_Image-23_14MR72-1165-1

MR111016_Image-24_14MR72-1167-1

MR111016_Image-25_14MR72-1167-2

89MR65

MR111016_Image-29_89MR-65-1169-1

MR111016_Image-30_89MR-65-1171-1

MR111016_Image-31_89MR-65-11773-1

14MR61

MR111016_Image-32_14MR61-1187-1

MR111016_Image-33_14MR61-1175-1

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MR111016_Image-35_14MR61-1177-1

MR111016_Image-36_14MR61-1181-1

MR111016_Image-37_14MR61-1179-1

MR111016_Image-38_14MR61-1183-1

MR111016_Image-39_14MR61-1185-1

MR111016_Image-40_14MR61-1185-2

MR111016_Image-38_14MR61-1183-1

MR111016_Image-39_14MR61-1185-1

MR111016_Image-40_14MR61-1185-2

